

POSSIBILITIES OF DEVELOPING COMMUNICATIVE SKILLS OF A PERSON OF SCHOOL AGE

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Abstract: This article discusses the scientific and theoretical features of studying the possibilities of forming communicative skills of a person of school age.

Key words: Educational system, communicative skills, theory, scientific analysis, pantomime, communicator.

Introduction.

After considering communication difficulties, the question naturally arises about the way and the means of prevention and correction. Specialists systematized some methods of social-psychological training. It makes sense to use a role-playing game, psychocorrective-mainly group discussion in behavioral training. Role-playing games can contribute:

- search for effective forms of mutual cooperation within the framework of cooperation, showing shortcomings, stereotypes of behavior;
- to strengthen the model of behavior leading to success, the purpose of which is to establish psychologically normal relations with other people;
- assimilation of the content of problems and contradictions of interpersonal and interpersonal relations of a certain person (psycho- and sociodrama). That is, it can be a tool for decomposition, integration, and as an addition, other methods can be included.

Objectives of the group discussion:

- *to eliminate the content of the problem and the conflicts of personal relations of a certain person;*
- *look for effective forms of cooperation within the framework of cooperation;*
- *reporting behavior in a role-playing game.*

That is, it can also be a tool for decomposition, integration, and can be included as an addition to other methods.

Psychological methods of innovative games have a positive effect on participants of correctional groups. Such psychological correction work with people should take into account the age, gender, profession and other specific characteristics of the participants of educational groups. Thus, teaching teachers elements and acting techniques accelerates their personal growth, allows them to understand the communicative features of their personality and use them correctly in communication with students, in general harmonizes their relationship with the people around them.

A comprehensive program has been developed especially for teachers, which includes the most important features of personal expression repertoire, as well as self-improvement of expression and development of non-verbal forms of communication. The program includes special self-massage techniques that develop "body feeling", relieve stress in the area of "personal clips", as well as exercises to improve facial expressions, gestures, voices, etc.

Today, various forms of social-psychological training are widely used, their goal is to study the psychologically literate communication of parents, leaders of different levels, actors, athletes, people suffering from various forms of neurosis and having communication difficulties. One of the main directions for overcoming psychological difficulties in communication is personal psychological counseling, reliable communication with students who do not have a good relationship with their peers.

Communication techniques are the ways in which a person communicates with people, his behavior and techniques in the process of communication - verbal and non-verbal means of communication. At the initial stage of communication, his technique includes elements such as the adoption of a certain facial expression, poses, the choice of initial words and tone of speech, movements and gestures. The first gestures that attract the attention of the communication partner, as well as facial expressions (smiles), are often involuntary, so communication people, to hide their position or attitude of the partner, take their eyes or hide their hands. In the same cases, there are many difficulties in choosing the first words, there are often speech errors, difficulties, there are a lot of interesting things about the nature of Z. Freud.

In the process of communication, some other methods and speech techniques are used, which are called feedback. Communication refers to the techniques and methods of obtaining information about the partner, which are used by interlocutors to correct their behavior during the communication process. Feedback includes conscious control of communicative actions, observing the partner and evaluating his reactions, and then changing his behavior accordingly. Feedback includes the ability to see yourself from the outside and correctly assess how the partner feels in communication. Inexperienced interviewers often forget about feedback and don't know how to use it.

Communication skills-communication skills and abilities. Children of different ages, cultures, and different levels of psychological development with different life experiences differ from each other in their communication skills. Educated and cultured children have more communication skills than uneducated and less cultured ones. The richness and diversity of the student's life experience is usually positively related to the development of his communicative abilities.

Communication techniques and techniques used in practice have age characteristics. Thus, in children of primary school age, they differ from high school students, and preschool children communicate with adults and peers differently than high school students. Communication methods and techniques of the elderly are usually different from those of the young.

Children are more impulsive and direct in communication, their technique is dominated by non-verbal means. Feedback is underdeveloped in children, and communication itself is often overly emotional. With age, these features of communication gradually disappear, and it becomes more balanced, verbal, rational, meaningfully economical. Feedback is also improved.

The ability to communicate is manifested in the selection of the tone of speech and specific reactions to the actions of the communication partner at the stage of predetermination. Teachers and leaders often have proud, Mentor tones due to undemocratic traditions formed in the field of business and pedagogical communication. Doctors, especially psychotherapists, when communicating with people, usually increase attention and sympathy.

In the socio-psychological literature, the concept of "business relations", usually aimed at ensuring negotiations, meetings and official correspondence, is aimed at the high efficiency of public speeches.

From the point of view of age psychology, the period from 16 to 25 years (human youth) is distinguished, which is characterized by the highest level of feelings. At a young age, the human mind is still a developed system, it already works according to its purpose, has the knowledge and skills necessary for the development of a profession, and the integrity of the functional foundations of the mind has not yet been determined, the cognitive ability is at a high level, which contributes to a more successful professional and intellectual development of a person. During this period, it is recommended to develop the communication skills of a person.

Summary

Our Assumption is that it is possible to achieve the development of a person's communicative skills with the help of developmental methods, tested through theoretical and empirical research. The results showed that after the training, most of the participants significantly improved their business communication skills, but not all were the same. Five of the eleven participants of the second group approached the participants of the first subgroup in their abilities, but only one of the four participants of the third subgroup reached the level of the participants of the second subgroup. In any case, the participants should further develop their business communication skills, including in order not to lose the achieved results. However, all participants were able to develop their communication skills. Thus, we proved that it is possible to overcome problems in communication and develop the communicative skills of a person with the help of methods of development of personality communication skills.

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